

The Level of Disaster Preparedness among the Employees of Selected Hospitality Establishments in Naval Biliran

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Abstract:- This study aimed to determine the different establishments that were prepared in case of the disaster strike that they think effectively to be safe their guest or to avoid accidents.

The study employed descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentage, mean, and rank to describe the findings.

In the demographic profile of the respondents, the majority of the age of employees was between 20-29 years. They operate mostly during lunch and evening. Most of the establishments in the Naval, Biliran are not prepared and they don't know what they are going to do if the disaster will come and lack equipment and tools. Results revealed that most hotels are exposed to a wide range of natural and man-made disasters preparedness in hospitality. The establishment lacks proactive emergency planning with any constraints which impede successful emergency planning. The result of the study and the following recommendations are proposed. The employees in the establishment should practice safety drills in case of an emergency, the establishment should have a proper and complete supply, equipment, and emergency kits. Emphasizing the relevant role of authority to demonstrate emergency management hotels and trying to convince them to adopt such practices to cope with emergencies effectively is a unique challenge.

Keywords:- *Disaster, Emergency. Preparedness, Planning Establishment.*

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

A. Background of the Study

Disasters in the hospitality industry have become a major issue as industry leaders look for solutions to deal with these unforeseen catastrophes, which pose a threat to the business's viability [1] and present many challenges for the private and public sectors [2]. The core of disaster resolution, according to Kash and Darling [3], is evaluating the current level of disaster planning and preparedness in the hospitality industry, as well as examining the relationship between organizational factors (type, size, and age). Disaster planning and preparedness are both important aspects of disaster preparedness. Natural disasters, such as floods, tsunamis, and typhoons, are commonly referred to as "Acts of God," whereas man-made disasters are referred to as socio-technical disasters.

Today's companies must be prepared for emergencies, which includes drafting crisis/disaster plans and training personnel. Whether it is a natural disaster, such as flooding, or a man-made disaster, such as fire, emergencies cannot be predetermined. Businesses are the economic drivers of communities, and many even become important in community-wide emergencies through the provision of services and goods essential in emergency response. Although businesses that have prepared for emergencies by training employees and creating disaster plans were more likely to have experienced a previous disaster, pre-disaster preparation is ultimately the key to successful workplace emergency response.

Today's workplaces need to be prepared for emergencies, which includes creating crisis/disaster plans and training employees. Emergency situations cannot be predicted, whether they are caused by natural disasters like flooding or man-made disasters like fire. Businesses are the economic backbone of communities, and many of them play a critical role in community-wide emergencies by providing critical services and goods. Despite the fact that businesses that have prepared for emergencies by training employees and creating disaster plans are more likely to have experienced a previous disaster, pre-disaster preparation is the key to a successful workplace emergency response.

Managers, on the other hand, appear to have a stronger perception of emergency preparation than their employees. Both management and staff must be aware of potential emergencies, and putting processes in place ahead of time can help resolve a variety of workplace scenarios. Employees' stress, worry, and overall fear, which are common during a tragedy or crisis, might be reduced with planning. Having an emergency plan in place can ensure that personnel have enough time to become familiar with processes and how to carry out all of the actions in the plan. Making an emergency plan and preparing ahead of time can help prevent property damage, injuries, and even save lives.

Provision of information not only on the emergency action plan but also on employee emergency roles requires the involvement of all employees, not just management. Therefore, following a brief workplace emergency planning training presentation focused on both employee and management roles, the goal was to characterize the level of disaster readiness. Any effect of the presentation on employee emergency planning knowledge was also assessed.

B. Statement of the Problem

They aimed to assess the level of disaster preparedness among the employees of selected hospitality establishments in Naval Biliran.

Specifically, it sought to attain the following:

1. To determine the demographic profile:
 - 1.2. Age:
 - 1.3 Sex:

- 1.4. Status:
- 1.5. Position.
- 1.6. Name of the Establishment

2. To determine the level of awareness in disaster preparedness among the employees in selected hospitality establishments:

- 2.1. Fire
- 2.2. Flash Floods
- 2.3. Typhoon
- 2.4. Earthquake

C. The Framework of the Study

In the course of its investigation, this study will rely on the following theoretical and conceptual frameworks as its main and solid underpinnings.

- *Theoretical framework.* This study is based in the Modern Disaster Theory by which, according to Jim Chen, treats Disaster Law as the finest portfolio of legal norms (2011:1121). (2011:1121). According to the Disaster Law and Policy, at first glance, disaster law seems to be nothing but a collection of legal rules that happen to come into play when communities have suffered severe physical damage, but at a deeper level, it is about assembling the best portfolio of legal rules to deal with catastrophic risks – a portfolio that includes mitigation, emergency response, compensation and insurance, and rebuilding strategies. The goal of disaster law is to improve the preparedness of all social institutions, including government and non-government entities, to anticipate a sudden, catastrophic occurrence and offer the best possible response.
- *Conceptual Framework.* The present study will focus on the level of disaster preparedness among the employees of the selected hospitality industry in naval, Biliran. The study will be conducted to determine the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, status, position, and name of the establishment. And Part II was to determine the level of awareness in disaster reduction management.

Fig.1: The Schematic Diagram of the Study

D. Significance of the Study

The results and findings of this study will be given favor to the following individuals:

- *Supervisor.* The study will help the management to orient the employees on the level of disaster preparedness.
- *Manager.* The result of this study will serve as a guide for the head of the establishment or the manager to improve the safety of the guest in terms of the disaster strike.

- *Organization.* This research will help to understand the organization's ability to successfully respond to and recover from disruptive events directly correlates to the effectiveness of their business continuity and IT disaster recovery training and awareness programs.
- *Guest.* The result of this study will lead the guest in preparing the effectiveness of the disaster preparedness in case of an emergency.
- *Customers.* The study will help to aware and prepared in case of the disaster is anytime and anywhere. Customers will do drills and be oriented so that they don't panic in that situation.
- *Researchers.* The study would be considered as a springboard for future research, looking into each of the Disaster Preparedness.

E. Scope of Delimitation

This study was focused on the disaster preparedness among the employee of selected hospitality establishments in naval, Biliran. The gathering of data was started in February to March 2018.

CHAPTER II

METHODOLOGY

This chapter discusses the methods and procedures that the researcher will use. This also specifies the research locale, research design, target, respondent, data collection procedure, data processing, and analysis so that necessary results and desired outcomes will be attained before further explanation and conclusion are made.

A. Research Design

The research design used in this study is a descriptive survey approach using the questionnaire to answer the research study's objectives. A questionnaire was utilized to gather data about the potential respondents which is the study of the level of disaster preparedness of the employees among the selected hospitality establishment.

B. Research Locale

The study was conducted of those selected hospitality establishments in the Naval, Biliran.

C. Data Gathering Procedure

In administering the data gathering the researchers have to undergo the proper procedure in gathering data. First, the researcher asked permission and approval from the college dean of the Naval State University to allow them to conduct a study legally. Second, the researchers asked permission to the manager of the establishments. After having permission from the manager to conduct the said research, the researchers proceeded to the employees within the establishment in naval Biliran. From that hospitality establishment, permission was asked from the manager and asked their employees in identifying respondents for the said research. When respondents were already identified, each of them was interviewed on that particular establishment.

D. Data Scoring

The questionnaire was designed to have qualitative measures because the research by nature was only done to describe the characteristics of things and phenomenon that can contribute to the hospitality industry in Biliran. This is the reason why this research can only be treated in a simple and basic statistics.

The data were score presented the following:

Weighted Mean	Description
15 – 20	Highly Prepared
10 – 15	Prepared
5 – 10	Unprepared
0 – 5	Highly Unprepared

E. Statistical Treatment

Data processing and analysis of the demographic profile, the researcher analyzed using frequency and percentages and Part II will use weighted mean.

CHAPTER III**PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA**

This chapter presents the results and findings of the study. The data were gathered and tabulated as follows.

A. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The table contains the demographic profile of the respondent in terms of Age, Gender, and Status.

Age	f	%
30 – 35	2	8.69
25 – 29	8	34.78
20 – 24	13	56.52
Total	23	99.99
Gender		
Female	20	86.96
Male	3	13.04
Total	23	100.00
Status		
Single	18	78.26
Married	5	21.74
Total	23	100.00

Table 1: Age, Gender, and Status of the Respondents

Age. The table shows for the demographic profile of the respondents, 20-24 years of age have 56.52 percent which is the highest, 25-29 is the highest rather than 30-35 the percentage is 34.78 and 8.69 which is the lowest.

Gender. As shown in the table out of the 23 percent's there were more females with 20 or 86.96 percent were the male was 3 or 13.04 percent. The result revealed that there were more female respondents in an establishment.

Status. As shown in the table out of the 23 respondents there was more single with 18 or 78.26 percent were married was 5 or 21.72 percent. The result revealed that there were more single respondents in the establishment.

Position	f	%
Server	6	26.09
Cashier	2	8.70
Receptionist	5	21.74
OJT	2	8.70
Sautee Cook	1	4.35
Housekeeper	3	13.04
Staff	2	8.70
Desk Clerk	2	8.70
Total	23	100.00

Table 2: Position of the Respondents

Position. As shown in Table 2, out of the respondents, server which have the highest 6 or 26.09 percent. Second, receptionist, 5 or 21.74 percent and the others was the lowest, housekeeper which is 3 or 13.04, desk clerk, cashier, OJT, staff have the same 2 or 8.70 percent and lastly was the sauté cook which is 1 or 4.35 percent. This means that most of the employees in the establishment were servers.

Name of the Establishment	f	%
D' Adaone Bar and Restaurant	4	17.39%
D' mei Residence Inn	5	21.74
Fragoch Tourist Inn	5	21.74
Marvin's Inn	4	17.39
Sandra's Traveler's Inn	5	21.74
Total	23	100.00

Table 2: Name of Establishment

Name of the Establishment. Shown in the table out of the respondent was more on D'mei Residence Inn which is 5 or 21.74 percent. D'Adaone Bar and Restaurant, Sandras Traveler's Inn, and Fragoch Tourist Inn have the same 4 or 17.39 percent, and lastly Marvin's Inn 4 or 17.39 percent. This means that most have the employees were at the D'mei Residence Inn, Naval Biliran.

B. Level of awareness in Disaster Preparedness among the Employees in Selected Hospitality Establishment

The table contains the Emergency Preparedness Supplies and Equipment kits in the Establishment Safety Drills Practices to prepare people for in case of Emergency in Tables 3 and 4.

Supplies and Equipment Kits	f	%
Fire Extinguisher	23	10.18
Fire Ladder	10	4.42
Dust Mask	13	5.75
Fire Axe	8	3.54
Fire Proximity Suit	7	3.10
First Aid Kits	18	7.96
Flashlight	23	10.18
Batteries	17	7.52
Wire Cutter	9	3.98
Emergency Rope, Bungees, and Cords	7	3.10
Shovel	2	0.88
Sledge Hammer	1	0.44
Claw Hammer	1	0.44
Brick Hammer	1	0.44
Metal Cutter	2	0.88
Gloves	13	5.75
Lifejacket of Lifebuoys	4	1.77
Foods	16	7.08
Water	19	8.41
Small Radio	11	4.87
Hammer and Nails	6	2.65
Sleeping bags, blanket or space blanket	16	7.08
Walkie talkie set	4	1.77
Boots hard toe steel shank	2	0.88
Cash Money	4	1.77
Portable Generator	4	1.77

Whistle to signal for help	3	1.33
Emergency rescue stretcher	2	0.88
Emergency Stove	2	0.88
Emergency Lights	15	6.64
Rescue boat	0	0
Safety Helmets	3	1.33
Total	226	117.67

Table 3: Emergency Preparedness Supplies and Equipment Kits in the Establishment

Table 3 shows that all establishments more on a fire extinguisher and flashlight which have the same highest, 23 or 10.18 percent, water 19 or 8.41 percent, first aid kit 18 or 7.96, batteries 17 or 7.52, foods and sleeping bags, blanket or space blankets was the same percentage 16 or 7.08, emergency light 15 or 6.64 percent and the lowest is rescue boat which is 0 percent. This means that the most available supplies and equipment in the establishment are fire extinguishers and flashlights.

Supplies and Equipment Kits	f	%
1. Be alert, don't panic	13.30	Prepared
2. Stay away from heavy objectives like bookcases, cabinets, and hanging accessories such as chandeliers or ceiling fans.	11.39	Prepared
3. Duck, cove, and hold fast in a covered position under a solid desk or table.	11.22	Prepared
4 When the shaking has stopped, walk out of the building in an orderly manner while still covering your head with clasped hands.	9.13	Unprepared
5. Proceed to designated open space.	14.96	Prepared
6. Look out for falling debris.	13.30	Prepared
7. Don't run or rush.	11.22	Prepared
8. Never attempt to go back inside the building once you are outside.	11.74	Prepared
9. Look around to make sure that everyone is okay.	12.78	Prepared
10. Wait for rescuers to arrive	13.65	Prepared
11. Stay calm	12.70	Prepared
12. Treat the alert if it is a real fire.	12.70	Prepared
13. Stop what your doing	14.96	Prepared
14. Start moving out of the building	14.61	Prepared
15. Move to the nearest exit	13.83	Prepared
16. Take the stairs	13.65	Prepared
17. watch for "smoke" signs	13.65	Prepared
18. Move to a safe distance	13.65	Prepared
19. Check with your local council about local flood plans or records	11.22	Prepared
20. Which detail problem areas	9.83	Unprepared
21. Ask authorities about relocation routes and centers	8.87	unprepared
22. If your area is flood-prone consider alternatives.	11.22	Prepared
23. Prepare an emergency kit	8.87	Unprepared.
24. Prepare a household flood plan	11.57	Prepared
25. Keep a list of emergency telephone numbers on display	8.61	unprepared
26. Check your insurance coverage to check if your flood damage is covered.	11.57	Prepared

27. To begin, assemble an emergency kit and advise a family communication strategy.	7.30	Unprepared
28. Know your surroundings	12.78	Prepared
29. Find out what your property's elevation is and whether it's flood-prone. This will help you understand how storm surges, tidal waves, and flooding will effect your house.	6.96	Unprepared
30. Determine the levels of dams in your area and whether they constitute a threat to you.	9.83	Unprepared
31. Learn Community typhoon evacuation routes and how to find higher ground. Determine where you would go and how you would get there if you	8.61	Unprepared
32. Make plans to secure your property.	7.91	Unprepared
33. Cover all of your home's windows. Permanent storm shutter	9.83	Unprepared
34. Provide the best window protection. Another alternative is to use 5/8' marine plywood that has been trimmed to fit and is ready to install to board up windows. Tape will not keep your windows from shattering.	10.70	Prepared
35. Install straps or additional clips to securely fasten your roof to the frame structure. This will reduce roof damage.	8.78	Unprepared
36. Be sure trees and shrubs around your home are well-trimmed.	9.65	Unprepared
37. So they are more wind resistant.	11.60	Prepared
38. Clear loose and clogged rain gutters and downspouts.	8.96	Unprepared
39. Reinforce your garage doors, if wind enters a garage. It can cause dangerous and expensive structural damage.	10.43	Unprepared
40. Bring in all outdoor furniture, decorations, trash cans, and anything else that isn't secured.	8.91	Unprepared
41. In the midst of a powerful hurricane. A loose object is a missile.	9.35	Unprepared
42. Determine how and where to secure your boat.	12.13	Prepared
43. if a high-rise building is prepared to take shelter on or below the 10 th floor.	11.43	Prepared

Table 4: Safety Drills Practices to Prepare People for in Case of Emergency

Table 4 shows that the highest percentage which is the same was proceeded to designated open spaces and stop what you're doing, 14.96 percent described as "prepared" and most of this table was described as "prepared". The lowest percentage was learned about the elevation level of property and whether the land is flood-prone. This will help you know your property will be affected when storm surge or tidal flooding is forecast, 6.96 percent, and the total of description was "prepared". This means that the establishment was prepared in case of an emergency.

CHAPTER 4

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter summarizes the findings, conclusions and offers recommendations for the study.

• Summary

This study aimed to analyze the level of disaster preparedness among the employees of hospitality establishments in naval, Biliran.

Descriptive statistics such as frequency count, percentage, mean, and rank were used to describe the findings.

Majority of the age of the respondents are 20-24 years old which is 13 or 56.52 percent.

The majority of the respondents are females.

The majority of the respondents are servers.

The majority of the respondents are single.

The majority of the respondents are working in D'mei Residence Inn.

The majority of the establishments are prepared in case of emergency.

• Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn.

The data also showed that the level of Disaster Preparedness among employees in selected hospitality facilities, as well as their age, gender, status, and job title, had a significant impact on proactive disaster planning. The hospitality sector will be able to provide the necessary resources, as well as effective training, if it is prepared and has an updated emergency plan with manager knowledge. To save lives and hospitality properties, safety surveillance and security solutions are critical. These aspects can also be used as a marketing tool for meeting planners and guests. Finally, it is necessary to grasp the emergency frameworks to lessen the effects and be well prepared before crises strikes. Furthermore, the loss of these frameworks is minimized during an evacuation in the event of a calamity.

• Recommendation

Based on the result of the study, the following recommendations are proposed.

- The employees in the establishment should be practice and perform safety drills in case of an emergency.
- The establishment should have a proper and complete supply and equipment in case of a disaster strike.
- In every establishment has a first aid kit in case of emergency.

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